

conditions where timely planting is not possible because of unavoidable circumstances, one is bound to transplant aged seedlings. In hybrid rice seed production, in spite of staggered seeding, simultaneous planting of male and female parents is preferred to avoid inconvenience and wasted labor. An experiment was therefore conducted during the 1994 wet season to find out the effect of seedling age at transplanting on flowering time in A, B, and R lines. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design using five cytoplasmic male sterile lines along with their corresponding maintainers, six restorer lines, and one check variety in three replications at a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. Sequential transplanting was done at an interval of 5 d using 15-50-d-old seedlings. Observations were recorded on days to 50% flowering.

The results showed that seedling age exerted a significant and positive effect on flowering; older seedlings at transplanting delayed flowering in all the lines studied. Instead of using seedlings of the optimum age (20 d), transplanting 15-d-old seedlings advanced flowering by 1 d in all the lines. When 25-d-old seedlings were used for transplanting, flowering delay was negligible in the R and B lines, but delay was 1 d in the A line. Flowering in the R lines was delayed markedly (3 d), followed by A and B lines (2 d), when 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted.

Restorer lines, which generally have a longer growth duration than their female counterparts, are sown first to produce hybrid rice seed. Therefore, at the time of transplanting, R line seedlings would be older than A line ones. Recent studies have indicated that the optimum standard of synchronization is that the female parent should flower 1 or 2 d earlier than the male parent.

Our study indicated that flowering was advanced by 1 d in A lines when 15-d-old seedlings were transplanted; it remained the same in B and R lines if 20-25-d-old seedlings were transplanted. In a hybrid combination involving a male parent with 10 d

longer growth duration than the female parent, simultaneous transplanting using 15-d-old A line seedlings and 20-25-d-old seedlings of B and R lines can be done without affecting the expected time of flowering. Transplanting seedlings aged more than 30 d showed positive and similar effects in delaying flowering in A, B, and R lines. The results in our studies indicate that similar information for the parents of commercial hybrids must be obtained in both seasons in the target area prior to large-scale seed production. ■

Storage potential of parental lines of hybrid rice

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To elucidate the storability of parental lines of hybrid rice, we studied seed quality parameters (such as germinability and vigor index) and some biochemical traits. Seeds of different parental lines of hybrid rice—A lines (IR62829A and IR58025A), B lines (IR62829B and IR58025B), and R lines (IR10198-66-2R, AS89044, Pusa 150R, C20, and C22) having superior germinability—were stored in cloth and 400-gauge polyethylene bags. The seeds were evaluated for seed quality parameters at bimonthly intervals for 12 mo. Finally, they were subjected to accelerated aging for 9 d in an aging chamber (40 °C and 100% relative humidity).

IR10198-66-2R and AS89044 (R lines) maintained prolonged viability, whereas deterioration was faster in C20. A lines usually recorded high germinability initially but deteriorated faster than their respective maintainers during storage. A similar trend was noticed in dry matter production and vigor index. Biochemical analysis showed a steady decrease in dehydrogenase activity and an increase in both

free sugars and electrical conductivity of seed leachates as the storage period increased. Among the containers tested, the polyethylene bag proved its superiority over the cloth bag in maintaining vigor and viability, probably because of less influence from external factors such as relative humidity or temperature. It is obvious from the study that, besides container and genotype influence, the male sterility system also has a key role in seed storability. ■

Dormancy of seeds of some rice hybrids and their parents

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The extent of seed dormancy in hybrids and their parents was investigated during the 1994 wet season. Harvested seeds from parents, hybrids, and check varieties were stored in paper bags and tested for germination at 5-d intervals. The study included the hybrids IR58025A / IR9761-19-R and IR58025A / IR29723-143-3-2-1R, male parent IR62829A, and check varieties Mandya Vijaya and IR20.

The results indicated that both cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, IR58025A and IR62829A, break dormancy 25 d after maturity and record more than 90% germination. The hybrid IR58025A / IR9761-19-1R recorded 72% germination after 25 d and 88% after 30 d. Its restorer took 30 d to break dormancy, with 84% germination. The other hybrid, IR58025A / IR29723-143-3-2-1R, recorded 92% germination after 30 d, whereas IR29723-143-3-2-1R did not germinate at all even after 30 d. It took 45 d after harvest to record more than 85% germination. Check varieties Mandya Vijaya and IR20 broke dormancy after 20 d. The results demonstrated that CMS lines IR58025A and IR62829A can be used for sowing

25 d after maturity. Restorer lines IR9761-19-1R and IR29723-143-3-2-1R can be sown only 30 and 45 d after harvest, respectively. It is safe to market the hybrid seeds 30 d after harvest. ■

Significance of stigma exertion in enhancing outcrossing in male sterile rice lines

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An investigation undertaken to study the floral characteristics of male sterile lines will lead to better outcrossing and enhanced seed set. Eight cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines were used for the study. Floral characters such as rate of stigma exertion, stigma length and

width, stigmatic area, style length, and natural seed set of these lines were observed during the 1995 wet season.

The natural seed set in these CMS lines ranged between 1.86% in IR68275A and 10.6% in IR58025A, with a mean value of 5.59%. Among the floret characteristics studied, stigma exertion showed a predominant influence on seed set. The mean stigma exertion rate ranged between 6% in IR68275A and 48% in IR58025A. IR58025A, IR68281A, and IR67684A showed a significantly higher percentage of stigma exertion. The significantly higher seed set (10.6%) in IR58025A was attributed to its higher stigma exertion rather than to any other floral characteristics. The genotype with the least stigma exertion (IR68275A) recorded the lowest natural seed set (1.86%). Genotypes with a higher rate

of stigma exertion recorded a higher style length, as observed in IR58025A, IR68281A, and IR67684A. Even though stigma exertion and style length in IR67684A were higher than in other genotypes, seed set was low (4.1%), indicating the linkage factor involved with cytoplasm for male sterility. In IR64707A, multiple stigmas were recorded in 3% of the florets.

Our results indicated that, among floral traits, better stigma exertion should be given maximum importance when developing desirable CMS lines. IR58025A showed maximum seed set (47.68%) and maximum style length (1.22 mm). Although genotype IR67684A showed many favorable floral characteristics for high seed set, it is undesirable because of the interaction of genome and cytoplasm on seed set. ■

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management

Effect of N levels and time of application on grain yield of hybrid rice

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During the 1995-96 wet season and dry season, we studied the performance of three hybrids—KHR1, ProAgro 103, and MGR1—using Jaya and Rasi as standard checks. This study included

growth and grain yield performance at four levels of N (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg ha⁻¹). Three schedules of N application were followed: three splits (50:25:25% at basal, tillering and panicle initiation), four splits (25% N at basal, tillering, panicle initiation, and 50% flowering), and five splits (25% N at basal, tillering, and panicle initiation and the remainder applied in two equal splits at 50% flowering and 10 d later). Grain yield differences among the test hybrids and varieties were significant during both

seasons. The maximum grain yields were recorded for ProAgro 103, Vikas, KHR1, and MGR1. Rasi produced 5-14% less grain yield than ProAgro 103. Varieties responded linearly to applied N levels up to 120 kg ha⁻¹. Grain yield differences were not significant among different schedules of N application, indicating that more than three splits of N application are not required for higher grain production by hybrid rice in Vertisol soils. ■

Crop management

Three-drying cultivation of rice: a new technology for rice production in drought-prone areas

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Shandong, China, has a dry spring and rainy summer. In Linyi district, for

example, mean annual rainfall is 872-949 mm, of which 125-150 mm (15%) occur in spring and 560-600 mm (65%) in summer. Because of waterlogging in the wet summer period, grain yields of rainfed crops such as maize, soybean, or sweet potato were often poor in low-lying farming regions. When rice was dry-seeded late in spring after fall

wheat, the medium-duration rice varieties could not ripen because of the shortened growing period. It was difficult to grow rice seedlings because of the lack of water in spring. Therefore, only a fall wheat crop could be grown in the region.

This paper reports research examining the ability to raise rice seedlings,